

A Study on Infrastructural Facilities Provided by Public and Private Schools in Hyderabad District, Telangana State

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Abstract

Education is a vital aspect of the development process as well as its goal. Under the primary education gets the highest priority and is considered the base of formal education. Primacy education is a basic requirement for development of state. It is also a basic requirement for increasing the overall productivity a society. Primary education was made free and available to all children in the age group six to fourteen in the state. The demand for primary education is not fulfilled making different efforts. Primary schools' infrastructure such as building, furniture and equipment's contribute to a learning process of students. The paper is associated with infrastructural facilities provided by in primary education schools in the state of Telangana.

Keywords: Education, Primary Education, Infrastructure in primary schools

1. Introduction:

Primary education is the main pillar on which the higher education functions properly. At present, in India primary education is a fundamental right for the citizens. Besides this, article 21-(A) executes the free and compulsory education for all children up to the age group 6 to 14 irrespective of caste, creed, class, race and religion. The fulfillment of this provision is mainly dependent on the educational facilities and teaching procedures available in primary schools. Wastage and stagnation are the basic impediment for universalization of primary education in India. Some factors are mainly responsible for these problems. Lack of educational facilities or unattractive educational facility is of the main responsible for these problems. To minimize these problems the Government of India has launched scheme known as Sarva- Siksha Abhiyan in the year 2001. It is a complete scheme for proper development of primary schools and universalization of primary education in the country. The main areas of Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan are infrastructure development, teachers training institutional changes, mid-day meal scheme, minimum levels of learning, joyful

and activity-based learning etc. Now, it is the time to observe how far the primary education is upgraded and improved in India with Sarva-Siksha Abhiyan.

2.Review of Literature:

Sotiropoulos and Patrinos (2004, 2018) stated that private returns to higher education have increased over time, raising issues of financing and equity. Social returns to schooling remain high, above 10 percent at the secondary and higher education levels. Women continue to experience higher average rates of return to schooling, showing that girls' education remains a priority. Returns are higher in low-income countries. (Abdullah, 2011) Quality education is a key to provide the right human resources for social and economic production sectors facilitating wealth creation and improving living standards.

Ahafo (2009) who observed that in modern society, family influence played a very important role in the academic life of a student.

Outlaw (2007) also supported by stating that effective learning involves partnership of students, teachers and parents. He also observed that families' involvement determines the emotional and material input that further determined the motivation level in students towards education.

Moraka (2001) noted that all children have certain needs, physical and sociological which when met contribute positively to their academic Achievement. These needs may include a conducive reading atmosphere, good food, playing ground, provision of books and other material and attendance at the best schools available.

3. Need for the study:

Present study aim is to know the physical facilities available in the primary education schools and facilities provided by the primary education schools.

4.Objectives of the study:

The main objective of the study is

1. To identify the physical facilities available in the primary schools.
2. To analyses the facilities provided by primary education schools

5. Research Methodology:

The study is based on the primary data. The primary data was collected by using the structured questionnaire. The secondary data collected using sources include various journals and internet websites.

Sample of the study:

The purposed sample of the study is restricted to 110 respondents.

7. Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table-1 The Mean Rank of Infrastructure provided by the primary education schools using Mann-Whitney Test

Ranks				
	Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Black board	Male	29	56.17	1629.00
	Female	81	55.26	4476.00
	Total	110		
Desks, Benches and Chairs	Male	29	54.16	1570.50
	Female	81	55.98	4534.50
	Total	110		
Television	Male	29	66.10	1917.00
	Female	81	51.70	4188.00
	Total	110		
Computer	Male	29	59.84	1735.50
	Female	81	53.94	4369.50
	Total	110		
Drinking Water Facility	Male	29	51.28	1487.00
	Female	81	57.01	4618.00
	Total	110		
Playground facility	Male	29	52.79	1531.00
	Female	81	56.47	4574.00
	Total	110		
Games and Sports room	Male	29	52.40	1519.50
	Female	81	56.61	4585.50
	Total	110		

The above table shows the mean ranks of Gender out of 110 respondents male and female were 29 and 81 responded infrastructure provided black board mean ranks of Male respondents were 1629.00 and female respondents were 4476.00. Desks, Benches and Chairs mean ranks Male respondents were 1570.50 and female respondents were 4534.00. and Chairs mean ranks Male respondents were 1570.50 and female respondents were 4534.00. Television mean ranks Male

respondents were 1917.00 and female respondents were 4188.00. computers mean ranks Male respondents were 1735.50 and female respondents were 4369.00. Drinking Water Facility mean ranks Male respondents were 1487.00 and female respondents were 4618.00. playground facility mean ranks Male respondents were 1591.00 and female respondents were 4574.00. Games and Sports Room mean ranks Male respondents were 1519.00 and female respondents were 4585.00.

8. Testing of Hypothesis:

Ho: There is no significant difference between Gender and infrastructure provided by primary education schools.

Ha: There is a significant difference between Gender and infrastructure provided by primary education schools.

Test Statistics

	Black board	Desks, Benches and Chairs	Television	Computer	syllabus Books	Drinking Water Facility	Playground facility	Games and Sports room
Mann-Whitney U	1155.000	1135.500	867.000	1048.500	1162.000	1052.000	1096.000	1084.500
Wilcoxon W	4476.000	1570.500	4188.000	4369.500	1597.000	1487.000	1531.000	1519.500
Z	-.138	-.275	-2.152	-.876	-.088	-.873	-.565	-.634
Aseem. Sig. (2-tailed)	.890	.783	.031	.381	.930	.383	.572	.526

To test the hypothesis Mann-Whitney U Test used to know the significance between gender and infrastructure provided by primary education schools grouping variable Gender and black board z value is -0.138 and p value is 0.890 is greater than 0.05% significance level. Gender and Desks, Benches and Chairs z value is -0.275 and p value is 0.783 is greater than 0.05% significance level. Gender and Television z value is -2.152 and p value is 0.031 is less than 0.05% significance level. Gender and Computers z value is -0.876 and p value is 0.381 is greater than 0.05% significance level. Gender and syllabus books z value is -0.088 and p value is 0.930 is greater than 0.05%

significance level. Gender and drinking water facility z value is -0.873 and p value is 0.383 is greater than 0.05% significance level. Gender and playground z value is -0.565 and p value is 0.572 is greater than 0.05% significance level. Gender and sports room z value is -0.634 and p value is 0.526 is greater than 0.05% significance level. Hence it concludes that the Gender and facilities provided by primary education schools television z value is -2.152 and p value is 0.031 is significant difference. Accept alternative hypothesis H_a .

9. Conclusion

This study is mainly concerned with the seen the availability of educational facilities for students in primary schools of Telangana State. After completion of analysis all the data collected from the head of the institutions it is found that most of the primary schools of Telangana State are lacking of providing television facilities and providing infrastructure like black boards, desks, computers, syllabus books, drinking water, playground and games and sport room etc. it could be contributory factors in primary schooling. The midday meal programmed appears to be functional in most of the schools visited. Also, at present Sarva Siksha Abhiyan has been trying to improve the conditions of primary education schools.

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